

Phospho-AKT

3.20.18

30 min.

#1

#2

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G: P-AKT film

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G

Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, **Lane 4: NIH-1**, Lane-5: NIH-2, **Lane-6: 16pM1**,
Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line **Lane 10: 16pF**

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

*Failed lines: These were lines derived from the 16pDel cohort with poor NPC marker expression, on quality analysis they were discarded as they did not express PAX6.

Phospha

Gapdh

3.27.18

#1

#2
✓

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G: GAPDH for P-AKT Film

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G

Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

#3
✓

Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, **Lane 4: NIH-1**, Lane-5: NIH-2, **Lane-6: 16pM1**,
Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line **Lane 10: 16pF**

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

*Failed lines: These were lines derived from the 16pDel cohort with poor NPC marker expression, on quality analysis they were discarded as they did not express PAX6.

Total AKT 155

3.20.18

#1 ✓

#2

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G: Total AKT Film

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G

Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, Lane 4: NIH-1, Lane-5: NIH-2, Lane-6: 16pM1, Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line **Lane 10: 16pF**

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

*Failed lines: These were lines derived from the 16pDel cohort with poor NPC marker expression, on quality analysis they were discarded as they did not express PAX6.

Total
GAPDH

3.27.18

#1 ✓

#2 ✓

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G: GAPDH for Total AKT Film

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1G

Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, Lane 4: NIH-1, Lane-5: NIH-2, Lane-6: 16pM1,
Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line **Lane 10: 16pF**

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

*Failed lines: These were lines derived from the 16pDel cohort with poor NPC marker expression, on quality analysis they were discarded as they did not express PAX6.